

TENSILE PROPERTIES AND POISSON'S RATIO OF PET NEEDLE-PUNCHED NONWOVEN FABRIC PREPARED BY THERMOCOMPRESSSION BONDING

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ABSTRACT

Needle-punched PET nonwoven composites manufactured by thermocompression bonding are being developed as an alternative material for under-cover of vehicles. This material is lightweight and low-cost, and has excellent sound absorption performance and durability. In this study, the tensile properties and Poisson's ratio of needle-punched PET nonwoven fabrics prepared by thermocompression bonding were measured. In order to reduce the difference in anisotropic properties between the machine direction (MD) and transverse direction (TD), nonwoven fabrics with a uniform thickness of cross section were prepared by adjusting the carding delivery speed during manufacturing. Subsequently, the specimen was formed by thermocompression bonding. Stress-strain curves of the 2 mm-thick specimens were calculated using a tensile tester and digital image correlation (DIC). The specimen thickness increased with increasing displacement along the tensile load direction in the needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric. This phenomenon started at the plastic region in the MD specimen and at the elastic region in the TD specimen. The Poisson's ratio in each plane was also calculated. Thus, the basic properties required to simulate the mechanical behavior of the needle-punched PET nonwoven fabrics prepared by thermocompression bonding were evaluated.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the recent spike in the demand for eco-friendly vehicles, the competitiveness of a vehicle in terms of fuel economy has been stressed upon. Customers are increasingly demanding vehicle noise reduction and the use of eco-friendly materials, to ensure their wellbeing as well as that of the planet. In addition, customers are also seeking good performance in terms of noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH), which are related to quiet driving. This has led to active research on the indoor noise reduction of vehicles [1-3].

Under-cover are applied to compact or large vehicles, including hybrid and electric vehicles, and play an important role in improving the fuel economy during high-speed driving and reducing noises generated due to chipping, sanding, and road noises from the road surface by minimizing the air resistance at the bottom of the vehicle body. They also contribute to improving the performance and service life of the vehicle by protecting the components therein, such as engines and transmissions, which are exposed to the external environment at the bottom of the vehicle body [4].

Currently available under-cover are laminated structures comprising glass-fiber-reinforced PP, which is an intermediate material, and skin-layered nonwoven fabrics. However, they are vulnerable to breakage by external impact, because the intermediate layer is made of a highly brittle material. In addition, the low-weight epidermal nonwoven fabric layer on the surface of the material could tear by chipping while driving, thereby leading to issues such as the exposure of the glass fiber [4-6].

To address such issues, composites are being developed using needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, which is a new alternative material that is lightweight, low-cost, and has excellent sound absorption performance and durability. The typically used nonwoven fabric is a uni-materialization material, which can be easily recycled. The material meets the design, production, collection, and recycling considerations required to reduce the use of hazardous substances. Material unification and simplification of existing products were also considered [4, 7, 8].

This study seeks to enable the development of composites using a needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric prepared by thermocompression bonding. Through tensile tests, the strain-stress curve and Poisson's ratio for each direction were obtained, and the results were analyzed. Thus, basic properties required to predict the mechanical behavior of needle-punched PET nonwoven fabrics prepared by thermocompression bonding were evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Preparation of nonwoven fabric

Nonwoven fabrics exhibit extremely different properties depending on the types of the materials used, their design, and techniques of combination and bonding [9-11].

The fibers for the nonwoven fabric used in this study were prepared by mixing short fibers for heat-resistant crystalline binders (fineness: 6.5De, strength: 4.02 g/De, and melting point: 180.22 °C) and regular short fibers (RSFs, fineness: 6De and fiber length: 51 mm), both of which were procured from Huvis [12], in the weight ratio of 4:6.

The nonwoven fabric used in this study was formed into a web with a uniform thickness of cross-section by adjusting the carding delivery speed, so that the difference in the physical properties between the machine direction (MD) and transverse direction (TD) would be less than 5%. The average values of parameters used were as follows: carding delivery speed, 0.43 m/min; movement speed of the nonwoven fabric, 0.246 m/min; doffer speed, 28.00 m/min; average cylinder speed, 812.30 m/min; speed of the cross lapping center conveyor, 0.8 m/min.

The needle-punched nonwoven fabric was prepared by physically bonding the fibers to the web using a needle. The primary needle punching speed was 600 rpm, and the secondary needle punching speed was 200 rpm. The movement speed of the nonwoven fabric was 1.2 m/min.

Via thermocompression bonding, the fibers in the nonwoven fabric were bound by compressing them with heat. This provides high tensile elongation and does not produce substances harmful to the human body. For the thermocompression molding of the nonwoven fabric, preheating was performed at 180°C for 90 s, molding was performed at a pressure of 100 kgf/cm² for 15 min, and cooling was performed for 75 s. A 2 mm-thick plate was formed using a mold, following which the plate was cut to the standard size of 150 × 25 mm for the tensile test.

2.2 Measurement of tensile properties

The Shimadzu Autograph AGS-X tensile tester was used to evaluate the mechanical properties, and ARAMIS from OMAGOM [13], a DIC system, was used to measure the strain. This system has two CCD cameras, each of which has six million pixels (2,750 × 2,200 pixels). By adjusting the distance between the cameras, it was possible to measure the displacement of an object of size ranging from several mm² to several m², with a resolution of 0.5 μm. In the tensile test, 25 mm of each end of the 150 mm-long specimen was held by the tensile sample holder (effective measurement length: 100 mm), and the specimen was stretched in the tensile direction at a rate of 5 mm/min.

Figure 1. Tensile tester and DIC system

The displacement-force graph was obtained using the tensile load values used in the tensile test and the displacement acquired from DIC. In addition, the engineering strain-engineering stress graph was plotted using the engineering stress obtained via dividing the tensile load by the initial cross-sectional area of a specimen, as shown in equation (1), and the engineering strain obtained via dividing the displacement by the initial length of the specimen, as shown in equation (2). The true strain-true stress graph was plotted using the relationship between the engineering stress and true stress, as shown in equation (3), and the relationship between the engineering strain and true strain, as shown in equation (4).

$$S = \frac{P}{A_0} \quad (1)$$

$$e = \frac{\delta}{l_0} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma = S(1 + e) \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon = \ln(1 + e) \quad (4)$$

where P is the tensile load, A_0 is the initial cross-sectional area, l_0 is the initial length of the specimen, δ is the displacement, S is the engineering stress, e is the engineering strain, σ is the true stress, and ϵ is the true strain.

Typically, if a material is stretched in one direction, its length along the perpendicular direction decreases in proportion to the elongation along the direction of stretching. This phenomenon can be expressed by Poisson's ratio, which is the ratio of the strain in the direction perpendicular to the tensile load direction to the strain along the tensile load direction, as shown in equation (5). Typically, the strain in the tensile load direction has a positive value, while that in the direction perpendicular to the tensile load direction has a negative value. Therefore, Poisson's ratio is always positive, and is expressed by equation (5).

$$\nu = - \frac{\epsilon_{\text{transverse direction}}}{\epsilon_{\text{load direction}}} \quad (5)$$

where $\epsilon_{\text{load direction}}$ is the strain in the tensile load direction, $\epsilon_{\text{transverse direction}}$ is the strain in the direction perpendicular to the tensile load direction, and ν is Poisson's ratio.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tensile properties of thermocompressed needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric

The tensile test specimen fabricated using the thermocompressed needle-punched PET nonwoven

fabric is shown in Figure 2(a). The density of the formed tensile specimen was measured for ten specimens, to be $0.77 \pm 0.005 \text{ g/cm}^3$. In addition, the marks from needle punching are visible on the XY plane (in-plane). The fibers are standing along the thickness direction (Z-axis) by needle punching (Figure 2(b)), and are laid obliquely with decreasing thickness due to thermocompression forming, thereby fusing the fibers (due to melting). Figure 2(c) shows the condition before thermocompression forming, wherein the fibers are intertwined. Figure 2(d) shows the condition after thermocompression forming, wherein short fibers for the binders are fused with other fibers.

Figure 2. Tensile test specimen of needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric; (a) TD tensile test specimen of thermocompressed needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, (b) Condition of the fiber along the thickness direction before thermocompression forming, (c) Condition of fiber along plane direction before thermocompression forming, (d) Condition of fiber along plane direction after thermocompression forming

3.2 Tensile test results

Figure 3. Displacement-force graphs of the specimens in each direction; (a) MD specimens, (b) TD specimens

Figure 3 shows the results of the tensile test conducted in the MD and TD. In this figure, the reaction force measured by the load cell is plotted against the displacement of DIC. The average difference in the maximum reaction force between the MD and TD specimens was approximately 8%, based on the TD specimens.

The averaged strain-stress curves are shown in Figure 4. The tensile test results reveal that the MD specimens exhibit 7.1% lower stress at a strain of 0.02 than the TD specimens, and that the maximum stress of the MD specimens is 4.6% lower than that of the TD specimens.

Figure 4. Strain-stress graphs of the specimens in each direction; (a) MD specimens, (b) TD specimens

3.2 Poisson's ratio

Figure 5. Displacement-strain graphs in each direction for the MD tensile load; (a) displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (b) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (c) displacement-strain graph of the XZ plane, (d) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XZ plane

Figure 5(a) shows the displacement-strain graphs, and Figure 5(b) summarizes the trend lines and approximation formula by expanding the elastic region. In Figure 5(a), a positive strain is observed in the tensile direction (X-axis) in the XY plane, whereas a negative strain is observed in the direction (Y-axis) perpendicular to the tensile direction. Thus, the specimen is elongated in the former, whereas its length is reduced in the latter. Therefore, assigning a positive value to the tensile direction strain, i.e., the denominator of equation (5), and a negative value to the direction perpendicular to the strain, i.e., the numerator of the equation, produces a positive Poisson's ratio, which is typically observed in materials. The XZ plane (out-of-plane), however, shows a different tendency. As shown in Figure 5(c), in the XZ plane, a positive strain is observed in the tensile direction (X-axis) under a tensile load, whereas the initial negative strain observed in the direction (Z-axis) perpendicular to the tensile direction turns into a positive strain. Thus, the thickness (Z-axis) of the specimen decreases and then increases.

This phenomenon is different from the results of a previous study [14], wherein a positive strain was observed in the direction (Z-axis) perpendicular to the tensile direction from the beginning of the test. However, in this study, the negative strain turned into a positive strain. A negative strain was maintained in the elastic region, but turned to a positive strain in the plastic region, as shown in Figure 5(d).

This may be because the structural strength of the specimens in this study, which were generated via the formation of fiber networks under thermocompression, was higher than that of the nonwoven fabric specimens used in the previous study [14]. That is, the negative strain (reduction in the thickness) in the direction perpendicular to the tensile load direction, which is observed from typical solid materials due to the initial strong bonding force, was maintained until the bonding force of the network was weakened and the fibers in the thermocompressed needle-punched fabric recovered their characteristics, as shown in the previous study [14], when there was a positive strain (increase in the thickness) in the thickness direction.

Figure 6. Displacement-strain graphs in each direction for the TD tensile load; (a) displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (b) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the XY plane, (c) displacement-strain graph of the YZ plane, (d) elastic region trend lines in the displacement-strain graph of the YZ plane

As shown in Figure 6(a), (b), and (c), the TD specimen exhibits a similar trend to the MD specimen. However, the strain along the Z-axis changes from negative to positive in the elastic region, as shown in Figure 6(d), which is different from that of the MD specimen.

Figure 7. Poisson's ratio graphs of the specimens in each direction according to the displacement; (a) MD specimen, (b) TD specimen

Poisson's ratio, which was calculated using the trend line equations of Figure 5(b) and (d), is shown in Figure 7(a). Figure 7(a) shows that Poisson's ratio in the XY plane (in-plane) is constant at 0.283, regardless of the strain. In the XZ plane (out-of-plane), however, Poisson's ratio linearly decreases as the displacement increases. In addition, a positive Poisson's ratio is observed in the elastic region. However, when the plastic region appears due to increase in the displacement, a negative Poisson's ratio is observed, and the thickness is increased.

Figure 7(b) shows Poisson's ratio of the TD specimen calculated using the trend line equations of Figure 6(b) and (d). While Poisson's ratio in the XY plane (in-plane) is constant at 0.249, it linearly decreases with increasing displacement in the YZ plane (out-of-plane). The reduction rate is higher than that of the MD specimen, and the positive Poisson's ratio turns into a negative Poisson's ratio in the elastic region. Thus, the increase in thickness begins at an earlier displacement in the TD specimen than for the MD specimen.

5 CONCLUSION

A nonwoven fabric with a uniform cross section was fabricated by adjusting the carding delivery speed during manufacturing to reduce the anisotropic physical property difference between the MD and TD, and a basic material for use as the under-cover in vehicles was fabricated by forming the fabric via needle-punching and thermocompression bonding. Tensile tests revealed that the difference in elastic strain between the MD and TD was less than 1%, and thereafter, less than 5% at the maximum stress. In addition, with increasing out-of-plane displacement of the needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric, Poisson's ratio also decreased. However, while a previous study reported a positive strain in the direction (Z-axis) perpendicular to the tensile direction from the beginning, the strain of the nonwoven fabric in this study turned from negative to positive with increasing displacement. Owing to this special phenomenon, if a constant Poisson's ratio defined for a general material is applied to predict the mechanical behavior, the error between the predicted behavior and actual behavior increases. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the tensile characteristics in order to identify the mechanical behavior of the needle-punched PET nonwoven fabric fabricated by thermocompression bonding, for application to under-cover of vehicles.

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